

Effects of prednisolone administration on clock gene expression and indices of circadian rhythms in healthy human subjects

Supplementary

Table of contents

Randomization procedure	1
Supplementary table 1	1
Supplementary table 2	2
Supplementary figure 1	3
Supplementary figure 2	4
Supplementary figure 3	5

Randomization procedure

Trial medication was packed by the principal investigator in identical bottles, which were subsequently given a color code (blue or red) and number (1 to 10) by an independent nurse. The nurse conducted block randomization by drawing from a bag containing 5 lots each of red and blue, ensuring that 5 participants started with prednisolone and 5 started with placebo in a random pattern. The study medication bottles were packed in individual brown paper bags labelled with ID numbers and a 1 or 2 indicating the order. The study investigator handed out the brown paper bags. Participants were instructed to take ½ a tablet (12.5 mg) upon waking as close to 07:00 as possible without perturbing their natural sleep:wake pattern, and ½ a tablet 12 hours after, as close to 19:00. The last three doses were ingested under supervision on the study day. Compliance and timing of intake was assessed by counting remaining tablets and by participants completing a drug diary. The investigator and participants remained blinded until full completion of the trial. Harms were systematically evaluated by investigator questioning.

Supplementary table 1: *Sequences for primer pairs and probes used.*

Gene	Probe	Color	Forward primer	Reverse primer
<i>HPRT</i>	5'-(56-FAM/ACA GAG GGC /ZEN/TAC AAT GTG ATG GCC/ 3IABkFQ/ -3'	ZEN	5'- CGA GAT GTG ATG AAG GAG ATG G-3'	5'- GTA ATC CAG CAG GTC AGC AA-3'
<i>BMAL1</i>	5'- /5HEX/AAA CAC CTC /ZEN/ATT CTC AGG GCA GCA /3IABkFQ/-3'	HEX	5'- GCC ACC AAT CCA TAC ACA GA -3'	5'- AGT ATC TTC CCT CGG TCA CA -3'
<i>PER3</i>	5' /5TEX615/TCA GCA AGA AAG CAG GAG CAA AGC /3IAbRQSp/-3'	TEX	5'- TCA TCA CCC TAC AGC TCC TAT C -3'	5'- GCT TAT GCT TCC CTT TCC T -3'
<i>NR1D2</i> (<i>REV-ERB-β</i>)	5' /5Cy5/ATC GAG TGC /TAO/ACC TGG GAT GAC AAA /3IAbRQSp/ - 3'	Cy5	5'- GGT AAT CCC AAG AAT GGT GAT CT -3'	5'- CAC AGT AGA ACC ATG CCA CTA A -3'
<i>NPAS2</i>	5'- /5Cy55/TGA CAA CAG ACG GCA GCA TCA TCT /3BHQ-3/ -3'	Cy5.5	5'- GCT GAT GTT GGA GGC ATT AGA -3'	5'- CCA TGA CAT CCG ACG GTA AAT -3'

Supplementary table 2: Side effects reported in the study

Side effect	Placebo n / total n	Prednisolone n / total n
Any side effect	3/10	5/10
Sleep disturbance	2/10	3/10
Unrest	1/10	2/10

Supplementary figure 1: CONSORT diagram

Supplementary figure 2: Graph of interstitial glucose levels in the study period showing more pronounced nocturnal increases in glucose during prednisolone (blue line), peaking around 2-3 AM despite no food intake. Blue and red shadings indicate SE. Dark grey shadings signify nocturnal periods (00:00 to 06:30).

Supplementary figure 3: Cortisol and bioactive GC activity during placebo treatment. A) serum levels of total cortisol and bioactive GC activity expressed in cortisol equivalent nmol/l concentrations. B) Ratio between total cortisol and bioactive GC activity expressed in percent with a fitted sine wave curve showing a mean free cortisol (%) of 5.1 (4.8 to 5.4) and an amplitude of 1.2 (0.5 to 1.9) and a fit (r^2) of 0.68.

